

Problematic issues of the State governance of the organization of Civil-Military Cooperation in some areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine

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Annotation. The history of CIMIC development has been analyzed. It has been established that the term "civilian-military cooperation (CIMIC)" was initiated in the NATO countries. The essence of CIMIC and the process of its beginning in certain regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine since 2014 have been researched. An expert survey was conducted to study the current status of the organization of CIMIC in Ukraine. According to the results of the poll, the problems of public administration of the organization of CIMIC in certain regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine were identified. The analysis of the identified problematic issues for their further solution was conducted.

Wars, as a part of politics, have been actively used throughout the development of humanity. The basis of any conflict was and remains the interests of the aggressor state, or the state that provoked aggression against itself and intends to win a further war. Usually, these are the political or economic interests. Countries that have waged wars, both in the past and in modern history, rarely had the character of wars of total extermination. After all, the destroyed state and its exterminated population will ultimately not be able to make any economic claim, and the occupation of large territories by the population of the country that won the war takes a long time. Although, such cases in a history are existing.

The conflicts of the present times are no exception to these rules. But with the development of international law and rules of warfare, the military structures are increasingly taking into account of the legal and ethical aspects of warfare. The reducing the collateral damage to the local population and forming a supportive attitude to the actions of the troops remain one of the main tasks of the military formations that adhere to civilized rules of war and do not wage war on total extermination.

The term "civilian-military cooperation" was initiated in the NATO countries. In the NATO forces, CIMIC is an integral part of today's multidimensional operations, encompasses all parties involved in conflict resolution, and facilitates mutual support for civilian and military components. [1]. The main purpose of such interaction is to achieve the goal set and expected by all stakeholders, taking into account the interests of the local population, all civilians (representatives of the international community, international and non-governmental organizations), and including the Alliance. The key to the success of such cooperation is the understanding the specifics of the planning process and the activities of each key actors and stakeholders [2].

CIMIC is a well-planned, systematic activity of military formations on interaction with local executive authorities, public organizations and citizens in order to form a positive public opinion on the activities of military formations and to provide favorable conditions

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for the fulfillment of their tasks and functions, including counteracting the terrorist threats [3].

The objects of civil cooperation include: civilians, their needs and level of their satisfaction, non-governmental organizations, international governmental and non-governmental organizations, system and structure of government, law enforcement agencies, social relations, industrial sphere and labor relations, infrastructure for providing livelihoods and social services, technogenic hazards, transport, trading networks, banking system, cultural and mental features of the region (traditions, customs), religious organizations and relations between them, objects information sphere and the information environment in general. Subjects include teams of CIMIC of military units [4].

Therefore, the system of CIMIC is the set of functionally interconnected subjects of military formations and objects of civil cooperation, as well as the technologies of influence on them in order to create conditions for successful accomplishment of tasks. [5]. So, the organization of CIMIC is a joint, purposeful, organized and continuous activity of the structures of CIMIC, aimed at establishing and maintaining relations with the objects of the civilian environment at the appropriate level.

The CIMIC team plans, organizes and maintains relations between military units and international, charitable, humanitarian organizations, local self-government bodies, citizens' associations and local populations.

Taking into consideration that Ukraine's military formations lacked significant years of experience in CIMIC, and only with the launch of the Anti-Terrorist Operation (ATO) in certain areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions in 2014 and in the course of the further Joint Forces Operation (JFO) conducted since 2018, the system of CIMIC in the Armed Forces of Ukraine was established and started to operate [6]. Because of the lack of scientific development in this field, it has largely determined the foundation for the creation of the Ukrainian legal framework for CIMIC in the preparation and execution of the operations (combat operations). First of all, the foreign experience, first of all, of the military formations of the NATO member states was highly useful. [7].

Therefore, the purpose of the research is to conduct an analysis of public administration of the current state of organization of CIMIC in certain areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine since 2014 and to identify relevant issues for their further resolution.

In order to study the current status of the organization of CIMIC in some areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine, an expert survey in the questionnaires form of was conducted. As the respondents were selected the servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine who had personal practical experience of performing combat missions in certain regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions. The sample was 20 respondents. The number of questions was 12.

The analysis of the results of the questionnaire is given below.

To the question "How did you get knowledge about the nature and features of work during the ATO and JFO?" the largest number (43%) of the votes were answered: "from briefings, meetings held immediately before the completion of the tasks". The answer leads to some further conclusions as:

- 1) The information received immediately before the task remains the highest quality information for the personnel of civilian-military cooperation teams in the area of actions. This information, on a case-by-case basis, contains the highest number of reliable data and the least amount of distortion. The tasks are more specific, clearly defined the expected result from the actions.

- 2) The answer options "gained knowledge during the training" and "gained knowledge when performing tasks in such conditions" scored an equal number of points (28% of votes).

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This indicates a sufficiently low level of training of the personnel of the civilian-military cooperation teams in the period of official training, and the further need to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in the work already in the course of practical actions. Of course, sometimes the acquisition of skills is more effective, but the percentages of the answers clearly indicates the low level of early preparation and trainings.

3) The answer “by self-study literature” was catastrophically low (3%), indicating both the lack of sufficient guidance documents and the literature needed for professional guidance, and the reluctance of some individual servicemen to study the requirements of existing few guides.

When asked, "If the knowledge were sufficient to perform combat missions during the ATO and JFO?" the highest number of votes (90%) was answered "yes".

This answer indicates a sufficient level of knowledge and experience of civilian-military cooperation teams' specialists and a certain level of their self-confidence and ability to accomplish tasks.

When asked "What difficulties did you encounter when completing the task?" the largest and equal numbers of votes were given to the answers: “lack of interagency interaction” (30%) and “lack of information about the phenomenon” (30%).

These answers indicate a lack of level of organization of interaction both within the components of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and interagency interaction. Accordingly, the problem of lack of the necessary information directly depends on the level of organization of interaction and current situation data exchange.

The problem of insufficient level of comprehensive support for the activities of the CIMIC teams is still acute, as a significant percentage (13%) of the military-civilian cooperation specialists voted in favor of "unsatisfactory comprehensive support".

When asked, "What do you think should be the principles governing the ATO and JFO?" the highest number of votes was given to the answers: “organization and rationality” (19%), “promptness” (16%) and “unanimity” (13%).

These results indicate a lack of organization in the work of the governing bodies, speed of decision-making, clear division of responsibilities and delegation of authority.

To the question "In your opinion, does the existing legislation meet the requirements arising from the ATO and the JFO execution?" the majority of votes were answered: "not fully compliant" (55%), and "poorly meeting existing requirements" (30%). The answer "fully complies" received the lowest number of votes (15%).

These results indicate the dissatisfaction of the CIMIC troops with the current state of legal support for their activities or actions of the Armed Forces of Ukraine as a whole in the area of the ATO and JFO.

To the question "What do you think should be changed in the existing system of action during the execution of the ATO and the JFO?" the largest number of votes was given to the answers: “to improve the organization process” (24%) and “to improve the training system” (21%).

These results of the answers testify to the understanding by the CIMIC teams specialists the need to improve the management system and the system of vocational training and to improve their qualification.

To the question "In your opinion, what contributed to the shortcomings in the organization of interagency interaction during the ATO and JFO?" the majority of votes were answered: “no concerted action” (50%). The second largest response was “poor public relations” (19%).

These responses indicate the dissatisfaction of those interviewed with the level of organization of interagency engagement and the understanding of the importance of

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establishing a sustainable and lasting relationship between the military and civilian components of the ATO/JFO and between the military and local civilians.

When asked, "What specific weaknesses have you noticed in leadership's management decisions regarding the organization of interaction during the execution of the ATO and JFO operations?" the highest number of votes was given: "low speed of transfer of management decisions and commands" (34%).

The second largest number was the answer "lack of situational approach in specific decisions (attempt to unify management decisions)" (16%).

These results indicate the dissatisfaction of CIMIC military personnel with the level of responsiveness of the military administration and the temptation in approaches to solving the set tasks without taking into account the particular circumstances of each case.

Asked "In your opinion, what principles should be used to prepare military personnel to perform combat missions during the ATO and JFO operations?" the highest number of votes was given to the answers: "knowledge and skills assessments" (17%), "good and skilled planning" (15%), "stimulating professional growth and development of related specialties" (13%), "pre-training" (12%).

These results indicate that CIMIC military personnel understand the importance of timeliness and early training, the need for quality personnel selection, the promotion of their professional growth and comprehensive development.

When asked, "What actions do you think are required to improve the ATO and JFO engagement?" Most of the votes were answered: "creation of a unified system of crisis response during the ATO and JFO" (27%), "implementation of foreign experience in crisis response during the ATO and JFO" (24%).

These results indicate the need to improve the operation of the general management system and the relevance of exchange of experience with foreign military partners.

To the question "Determine the role of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in Ukraine's anti-terrorist security system (ATO/JFO experience)", the largest number of votes was given to the answers: "secondary" (38%), "major" (24%).

On the question "Determine the place of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in the system of anti-terrorist security of Ukraine (ATO/JFO experience)" the largest number of votes was given to the answers: "In the subordinate executives chain" (38%), "In the coordination chain" (34%).

The results of the responses indicate uncertainty with the answers of those who answered the questionnaire regarding the role and place of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in Ukraine's anti-terrorist security system. This may be a consequence of the transfer the leadership from Security Service of Ukraine in ATO to the Armed Forces of Ukraine during the further JFO conduction and the slow restructuring of CIMIC teams to the present day, as the issue concerned the modern experience of the ATO and JFO.

Thus, the results of the survey indicate that existing legislation and guidelines do not fully meet current requirements for organizing combat missions by CIMIC teams and groups in certain areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions. Also, the respondents' answers indicate the urgency of the issues of improvement of public administration regarding the organization of interagency cooperation of management bodies, increasing the level of pre-training of personnel, comprehensive support of CIMIC groups and teams.

Thus, it may be noted that the increase of CIMIC forces and their resources will have a significant impact on the interaction of the components of the security and defense sector of Ukraine with local residents, public and international organizations, with media and, accordingly, will improve the efficiency of the fulfillment of the assigned tasks. Therefore, the issues raised will be explored in further scientific research.

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